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SPIRITUAL POTENTIAL AND ITS ROLE IN MODERN

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigates the essence of spiritual potential as well as its role in modern society. From a sociological approach, as well as the survey, revealed its structure and unlike the moral and ethical development. The necessity of the development of the spiritual potential disclosure of individual personality for the sustainable development of society as a whole.

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Today, when the volume of spiritual life tends to zero, when the material and technical components have a greater impact on human development than the spiritual, it is important to note that the management of the process of the spiritual potential of the individual becomes of secondary importance, fades into the background. The main qualities of a spiritually rich personality are formed when the thirst for new knowledge is significantly high. If a person has a bad foundation that is insufficient for the necessary spiritual development of a person and his spiritual potential, then this deficiency is difficult to fill in the future. However, despite the much-needed role and significance of the spiritual potential in our society, the study of this term, as well as its structure, role in social relations and significance as an object of management are still insufficiently explored.

It should be noted that the very concept of spiritual potential is quite capacious and multifaceted. The spiritual potential of modern society is the very core of society, a multifaceted and developing complex, the structure of which includes not only literature, art and science. In modern conditions, an important role in the development of spiritual potential is played by the socio-economic, political and other spheres of public life, since the spiritual potential of a person is the degree of power of the hidden capabilities of the entire intellect, fed by both the material and spiritual spheres. At the same time, the decisive role is played not so much by the quantitative side - capacity building, as by the qualitative one - the internal need for the development of cultural values and the realization of potential opportunities [1, p.59]. A person, processing and assimilating, if desired, everything that culture gives him, applies it in his practice, actively searches for something new, grows creatively.

Spiritual potential has a direct impact on creativity, as well as on the moral parameters of the individual. The opposite effect is also clearly visible: the more active the creative activity of the individual, the shorter his path to comprehending the problems of spiritual values, and enriching his spiritual potential.

Literature often identifies spiritual and moral elements in social potential. In our opinion, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of spiritual and moral potentials. Spiritual potential is more capacious in content and includes moral, artistic, aesthetic and intellectual components, hidden and realizable capabilities of individuals, groups or organizations. The moral potential is understood as a set of norms and values that are distributed in society, expressed in such concepts as goodness, mercy, salvation, universal happiness. Spiritual and moral potential includes the moral, ethical and intellectual part of this subpotential [3 p.170.]. Which, in turn, is also connected with the worldview, political and value beliefs, as well as the active life position of the individual in modern society. The structure of the spiritual potential includes the objective and subjective components of the parties. The objective component is represented by intra-group, organizational relations and values, norms, knowledge, ideals, models of personal qualities, the totality of which further forms the intellectual, value and psychological component of the spiritual activity of society. The subjective side includes the moral and ethical, artistic and educational, ethnic and psychophysical component of the spiritual potential.

In modern conditions, the spiritual potential is subordinated to the tasks of building a society with a comprehensive development of the individual, as well as more and more complete satisfaction of material and, above all, spiritual needs, accompanied by the improvement of political and cultural progress, which, in turn, has a positive impact on the development of science and technology, the accumulation of the spiritual potential of society. A. Clark in his book draws attention to the discrepancy between the inclinations of a person and the possibility of their implementation. He believed that "for many years, intelligent beings have lived on our planet, people who could conduct symphony orchestras, derive theorems of pure mathematics, hold high-ranking positions, if they had the opportunity. But many people spend most of their free time in vain, only a couple of times in their whole lives comprehending the powerful, but deeply hidden possibilities that their mind has". Undoubtedly, the problem of realizing one's capabilities has always existed, although it has constantly changed. Certain adjustments to it were made by the everyday reality of a particular time in which mankind developed. Today, this is facilitated by modern technologies, their advanced development that does not stand still, expanding our understanding of the world and the choice of a place in life.

Let us turn to the necessity and significance of spiritual potential in the life of society. The reality of the spiritual potential is connected with the ability to possess sufficient power, but the power is “secret”, unrevealed, unconscious.

In short, the dictionaries of synonyms of the first stage are mainly composed of lists, the vocabulary is organized on the basis of thematic principles, used to teach rhetoric, to understand the subtle semantic differences of words and to use them in speech. It is observed that not only lists, but also their explanations are given, the comments also contain information about the historical development of synonyms, whether they are specific to oral or literary language, whether they are their own or assimilated layer word.¹

The presented article includes national-cultural outlook by zoonym components and the importance are discussed. Zoonyms are used widely to give advice, to show the right way, to give a lesson, to enlighten the philosophy of life, human and nature, human and the universe, human and so on.²

The article presents a comparative analysis of paremias containing the names of food products and expressing the specific characteristics of the Russian and Uzbek linguistic cultures. As a material, Russian and Uzbek paremias are used, containing the names of food products, analysis of proverbs and sayings of the Russian language and their comparison with Uzbek proverbs and sayings allows you to add new details to the gastronomic picture of the world that has developed among the two nations and have been consolidated in the language.³

Since computers started to be introduced in language learning (and in education in general) people have rightly asked whether the investment we are making in these technologies gives us value for money. As digital technologies have taken a hold in society in general, this particular question is not asked quite so often, but it is still important to make sure that the technologies that we have available are used effectively.⁴

The article discusses about studying of a propaedeutic course of the Russian literature in a context of the theory of intercultural communications. In the presented scientific direction, the most perspective are problems of comparative-historical, rather-typological studying different national literatures.⁵

The language portfolio is considered as an instrument of self-realization, self-esteem, self-perfection. An excerpt of a practical lesson in the discipline Russian language with gaming technologies and a table to test the acquired skills of students with a professional orientation based on the results of the lesson are given.⁶

The main criterion for evaluating literary translation is not only close to the original text, but

¹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2022). STAGES OF ENHANCEMENT OF SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *International Journal of World Languages*, 2(1).

² Tosheva, D. (2016). National-cultural outlook onto the zoonym component aphorisms. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 4(03), 22-25.

³ Maxmutovna, M. L. (2022). LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF GASTRONOMIC PAREMIAS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(1), 111-116.

⁴ Bozorova, N. X., & Salixova, Z. A. Using Technology to Assist in Vocabulary Acquisition and Reading Comprehension. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 213-215.

⁵ Sharipovna, B. M. (2020). Studying of a propaedeutic course of the Russian literature in a context of the theory of intercultural communications. *Academy*, (4 (55)).

⁶ Shodiyeva, D. Y. (2019). LANGUAGE PORTFOLIO-A TOOL FOR SELF-REALIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL-LANGUAGE COMPETENCIES OF A STUDENT. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 131-135.

also preserves the style of work and the individual style of the author. In this short article we will try to find out why you need a translator to adequately cope with the solution of the designated contact problem.⁷

People do not understand everything when they are born, but have to learn everything so that they are able to understand. Take learning Foreign language for example; not everyone can understand it, but some non-native speakers can use the language very well. This is not only the case with foreign language, but also other subjects. Therefore, during the learning process, one might find that some people can learn every subject or several subjects very quickly and well. On the other hand, some people have problems learning.⁸

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.⁹

A complex approach to personnel training is necessary in the learning process, therefore, in the Russian language classes, we pay great attention to the formation of students' language competence through professional vocabulary and terminology learned by them in the classroom.¹⁰

The Renaissance in Central Asia resulted in the greatest achievements in the political, economic and spiritual life of society. During this period, political and legal sciences, new literature and art, medicine, philosophy, and a new aesthetic consciousness were created.¹¹

As of now, the state policy of women, including women, in Uzbekistan, to protect the legitimate and social interests of women, to ensure full participation of women in the political life of the country, to ensure gender equality and reproductive health, is highly appreciated by the world community, namely, the International Labour Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization.¹²

Throughout the life of mankind, there are enduring spiritual needs, which have always been satisfied by products of spiritual production that are different in form, but similar in figurative and mental material. But, among other things, today we can also talk not so much about economic and political crises, but more about the spiritual. Enrichment with truly spiritual components, and not false values, directly affects the potential of the personality of each individual. This is evidenced by the results of the study. As an example, we can consider our study on the state of spiritual culture in society.

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⁸ TX, A. S. A. Learning Strategies and Learner Characteristics. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 206-208.

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